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Research Article

**MISMANAGEMENT DUE TO COMMUNICATION ERROR IN
PUBLIC HEALTH CARE CENTRE**¹Sidra Shabir, ²Ms. Sana Sehar, ³Muhammad Afzal, ⁴Dr. Syed Amir Gilani.¹Student. The University of Lahore, ²Assistant professor, The University of Lahore, ³associate professor. The University of Lahore, ⁴Dean faculty of allied health sciences. The University of Lahore.**Article Received:** September 2019 **Accepted:** October 2019 **Published:** November 2019**Abstract:**

Study scenario is reflecting mismanagement of fundamental needs for patients in hospital and poor Communication as it is very significant tool in problem solving process. One should be very careful in giving ideas while talking and sharing his views. Although we don't focus on deliverance of things but it's very important because it pursue others to understand what you were trying to convey them.

Communication in this study is the foundation stone of neural health care. Effective communication is not only important for meeting the patient's needs and providing safe, high-quality, and patient-centered care, it is important how we manage healthcare delivery.

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INTRODUCTION:**Incident:**

On my clinical duty 14 NOV 2019, I observed an issue regarding communication errors which leads to mismanagement. My duty was in Emergency ward where an enormous number of patients presented to us with RTA problems due to bus accident. The number of patients over more than patient were laid on the bunches as well as the drip set were picked up in the hands of patient relatives. Similarly, some of the drip set were picked in hands of the relatives during IV infusion as there were no IV-stands for them. At first I informed the head nurse of the ward he said arrange from another ward. I along with my colleague went to surgical ward and asked for IV stands the head nurse give us all the extra IV stands and beds. I and my fellow along with the help of ward boy bring the stands and bed from surgical ward to emergency. We were very lucky because the present ratio of patient at the time of incident were low therefore we find the stands from surgical ward.

Reason for selection:

I selected this topic because the scenario is reflecting mismanagement of fundamental needs of patients in hospital poor management of the emergency, so therefore, I select this topic.

Identification and Description of management process:

By observing this scenario and discussion with my colleague and also with the clinical faculty we identified that by application of problem solving management process we overcome this problem because it is clearly stated in the above scenario the shortage of equipment's in ward, patients and their relatives were also complaining. We approached to different resources but instead on discussing they gave their own justifications then our team leader give us idea of bringing the stands and beds from surgical ward which was very helpful for us. Communication is very important tool in problem solving process. One should be very careful in giving ideas while talking and sharing his views. Although we don't focus on deliverance of things but it's very important because it pursue others to understand what you were trying to give them.

Another important factor is the choice of problem solving context, which is further divided into solution focus and causal focus.

These two are the most common and important factors which are intermingled. When we face such

an issue it is always convenient to become solution focused although it is important but on the other hand we should indulge ourselves into in cause focused in which one must have to critically think and want to bring about a change which is always possible with the cooperation of others and this is one of the most important leadership role. It is not limited to just one solution but focuses on the results that may be encountered after the solution is presented. These things may seem theory based, but to some extent they are being implemented. Other solutions have been taken and combined with the above mentioned factors. Solving a problem is always challenging and many problems can occur when solving a problem. Sometimes you may make a mistake in identifying a problem that may also correct you incorrectly.

LITERATURE:

Problem solving may seem that one person can take control but in actual a group participates to bring about things done in a manner able way. We give decisions to solve a problem while on the other hand problem solving is a broad way where in authority individuals have to take several decisions. In our scenario as we mentioned that management is giving justifications it means that they are trying to solve the problem but it's not totally eliminated.

According to Vesterinen, Health care is changing dynamically. The economic plight is causing problems for the nurse manager to work and to hire professionals, disrupt staff, create a healthy work environment, and increase client demand. Response to these issues requires further expertise in management (Vesterinen et al., 2017).

As it is mention in the scenario that staff said that arrange the IV stands from the surgical ward so it is clear that if communication is good you can arrange these things in such conditions.

According to Lockwood, Communication with others is important in all health care and problem solving activities. The nurse must communicate clearly with the people she is assigned to, communicate with other nurses, interact with doctors and health professionals as well as patients and families. Examples of care should be used to clearly illustrate ideas that provide meaning because people may interpret things that were not intended. Because communication goes in both directions, listeners should take an active role to ensure a sound understanding. (Lockwood, 2016).

Example:

One of the example of the miscommunication during the patient's report of pain, the nurse assume that the patient asked for pain medication every 2 hours and complained all of the day, the listener could assume that this was just a difficult and complaining patient. Another accurate communication is that the patient complains of severe pain every 2 hours because his wound is red, swollen, and drains out.

It is a two way process and following would be exchange of questions that might be possible.

- More question asked: I'm not sure I assumed that. Could you explain again?
- May be: I understand you by saying that the wounded culture was taken. Is that right.
- Ask for more information: How much is a drainage? (Lockwood, 2016).

Core Leadership Competencies

8

(Wiwanitkit, 2002)

Explanation of situation in problem solving steps and strategy:

Although, miscommunication is one of the major cause of mismanagement of emergency departments which is already a 24/7 a chaos place of work in a hospital. It is not always easy to solve a problem as there are several facts which one should must considerate to solve a problem. As in our scenario

problem is that no one is trying to make its full effort to eliminate the problem. If I am at the manager's designation it's my responsibility to empower others to fellow and obey one chain of command to avoid the risk of communication error. At that time possible Information is collected from ward boy, head nurse and the patient and it was expected that everyone will work at its best.

Functions of Management

Management Process

(Adapted from Carroll & Gillen 1987, pp. 38-51)

15

We gathered information from different resources in order to validate the information provided. We should discuss it with every resource of information so that everyone should take responsibility and remind those rules and regulations so they tell what was wrong about the situation to reflect the root cause of the problem. The important achievement in this step is to point out the problem in order to see either it requires minor adjustment or major change.

There are three main factors in which I would

categorizes this issue which involves Human, Policy and some technical factors as they greatly effects our current hospital setup. Everyone wants to earn for living and wants to enjoy life but downfalls is the part of life and I learn from them through which I can initiate many other important things which may help to modify behaviors of not only yourself but it is also helpful for others. Again there comes discussion on the policy maker, how they make policies and methodology or medium use to convey the important information and competency to implement the

policies and also aware about the outcomes he/she face and how they act when such conditions appear and how they respond in such circumstances. If I were at that stage I will coordinate others skillfully and resolve the issue, it is possible through the above questions and use strategies used in management.

DISCUSSION:

My study scenario is reflecting mismanagement of fundamental needs for patients in hospital and poor Communication as it is very significant tool in problem solving process. One should be very careful in giving ideas while talking and sharing his views. Although we don't focus on deliverance of things but it's very important because it pursue others to understand what you were trying to convey them.

Communication in this study is the foundation stone of neural health care. Effective communication is not only important for meeting the patient's needs and providing safe, high-quality, and patient-centered care, it is important how we manage healthcare delivery.(Merlino, 2017).

In this study the nurse practice communication skill to provide standard nursing care. Structures of management, leadership and governance should be strengthened to ensure that plans for the purchase and maintenance of medical equipment are developed and implemented(Moyimane, Matlala, & Kekana, 2017).

CONCLUSION:

Communication is very important tool in problem solving process. One should be very careful in giving ideas while talking and sharing his views I should take personal actions and involve others in coordinating the solution. As a manager I will invite another group or person to solve the problem. At first I will approve my decision of personal actions and then take action. In this way others will act upon an action taken and report any communication error. In this step we will focus on the feedback and if it is implemented correctly then we approach to other processes.

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